

“Celebrity Obsession: A Budding Syndrome Amongst Adolescents”

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Abstract: Interest in the famous celebrities seems to be a human nature that goes as far back as recorded in the history. In ancient times, people created their Gods as very human-like beings, inclusive of all the righteous virtues as well as the character flaws. Humans are customarily fascinated by those they see as glamorous and charismatic. In the contemporary world, this phenomenon is being facilitated by the celebrities. Today, adolescents are exposed to an immense range of influential celebrities and their captivating way of life through television, current youth culture, print media and the Internet which make these celebrities a part and parcel of our daily lives. Celebrity obsession generally gets limited attention or ignored while studying factors influencing the phase of adolescence. This study aims at defining the concept of celebrity obsession and explaining it as one of the emerging phenomena among the adolescents by taking Albert Bandura’s “Social Learning Theory” as its theoretical background. Past literature and studies are examined, appropriate examples are cited and the role of these celebrities in shaping up lifestyle of adolescents is discussed in this study. This study also presents celebrity obsession in light of different type of fan following during adolescence.

Keywords: Celebrity Obsession; Adolescents; Mental Health

1. Who is a Celebrity?

The term “Celebrity” is borrowed from the middle French word ‘celebrite’; middle Latin word ‘celebritas’; from ‘celeber’ which stands for frequented, well known, famed, or honoured. It refers to the popularity, fame, glory, prominence and public attention granted by mass media, to an individual or groups, but is generally applied to the person or group of people (celebrity couples, families) who receive such a stardom. In common words, “celebrity” is a famous person, usually in entertainment, politics, business or sports industry. When seen in a positive light, celebrities are often depicted as individuals possessing some skills and abilities that are beyond average people. A common individual may become a celebrity through a wide range of ways, i.e., either by their professions, hobbies, personality, unbeatable talents, achievements, career, or even by complete coincidence. The majority of celebrities are: Actors, Athletes, Musicians, Political figures, Models, Journalists, Reality TV show participants, Spouse and child celebrities and others like cartoonist, photographers, radio jockeys, authors, YouTubers, poets, social media influencers, etc. Brad Pitt, Prince Harry, Cristiano Ronaldo, M.S. Dhoni, Michael Jackson, Taylor Swift, Steve Jobs, J.K. Rowling, Enrique Iglesias, Donald Trump, are a few among the more obvious examples of celebrities.

Without any doubt Celebrities are ordinary folks just like us, but such thought seems to be more rational in real life. Along with the tremendous globalisation and modernisation, celebrities are often 'idolised' and 'looked up' by common people like they are some objects of charm, fascination, marvel, and wonder and even have inferred a 'god-like' status in society. This is so because humans are born with a natural tendency to find someone or something for glorification, reflection, manifestation, affirmation and authority either as a guardian, hero, mentor, or protector. It is very natural for humans to get impressed by another human being, idolise them as their role model and then try to be like them in every possible way. In this era of internet and trend of social networking, Celebrities have become that role model as they have a very strong emotional and psychological impact at every age group, both negative and positive, in life as well as in death.

2. Who are adolescents?

Adolescence is a transitional period of physical, cognitive, and psychological development in human beings that occurs from the onset of the puberty and lasts up to legal adulthood. It is usually associated with the teenage years, i.e., between age of 13 and 19 years, but sometimes its expressions may begin earlier during the pre-teen years (between age of 9 and 12) and end later sometimes. This could be a phase of both disorientation and discovery. The individuals belonging to this age group are known as adolescents.

3. What is Celebrity Obsession?

An 'Obsession' is a persistent idea or impulse that continuously forces its way into consciousness, sometimes because of unreasonable ideas also. The characteristics of any form of obsession in an individual can be observed very easily and physically identified. 'Celebrity obsession' is an emotional state in which celebrities become so important to an individual that they are always thinking of them, in a way that seems extreme to others. Perhaps adolescents are the most influenced group by these celebrities since adolescence is a reflective age of peer pressure, role conflict, having uncertainty and confusion about their aspirations and future goals, all of which makes them easily prone to hitches, complications and distractions.

In today's era, along with the various physical, social, emotional and psychological factors, celebrity obsession has emerged as one of the most dominant aspect which seem to affect the adolescents, as they have a propensity to get attracted and influenced very easily by the glamorous world and develop their ideologies accordingly and try to look likewise because they want to be the best among their peers. Celebrities are often portrayed as glowing examples of perfection in front of adolescents by their elders, when they get any award and also as immoral when they get associated with any scandal. That is why, celebrities are sometimes disliked by some adolescents for their recognised achievement, and they may have a love or hate or love to hate relationship with these celebrities. Madlela (2014) confirms that the adolescents imitate the celebrities as they consider them as trend-setters and believes it to be acceptable norm for men and women in society

Celebrity obsession exists solely as a collection of individuals' desires for increased celebrity viewing. In Today's world, celebrity obsession may often be perceived as a way of 'escapism' or 'distraction' from the

challenging realities of everyday life of adolescents. Celebrity obsession can also be viewed as a means of reverie, far away from the reality of life. According to Battaglia (1995), adolescents often try to execute their ideas and creativity indirectly through their actions and body language by going through a course of self-realisation and countersignature of their social status, viz their language, fashion sense, gestures, appearance and achievements. This process is adapted during adolescence for 'rebuilding' and 'fixing' the unstable state of the "self" and reforming one's personal and social identity. The adolescents try express their zeal through new technologies and on social medias. They seek to define and brag who they are via their language, possessions, dressing sense, hobbies, physique, hairstyles, triumphs, group associations etc.

Accordingly, celebrities through various medias like magazines, sports league, political events, music, movies, drama series, news, reality shows, celebrity talk shows, celebrity interviews, advertisements etc. often provide various options from which adolescents targets their thoughts, choice, goals, career, dreams, opinions, preferences, and associations.

“In a market where years of experience can be outbid by a squirt of hairspray, it is not learning but looks, not the cerebral but celebrities that mark the winners.”

(Hartley 1996)

Celebrities repeatedly have fame similar to royalty and as a result, there is a strong curiosity among adolescents about their private affairs and because of high visibility of celebrities' personal lives, their successes and failures also become very public. Adolescents were seen to be so excited for the wedding of Prince Harry and Meghan Markle as if they themselves were an invitee there; or the checking in of Demi Lovato twice in the rehabilitation centre due to overdose of drugs have left her fans shocked and heartbroken; or the journey of Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam from being a devoid boy to be known as 'The Missile Man' of India to becoming the President of India works as an inspiration for numerous of youths; the accidental death of Paul Walker have left his fans into deep devoid and agony etc. are the most recent examples that shows how celebrities have become an important segment of life of commoners especially their fans..

4. Theorising Celebrity Obsession

The theoretical framework that supports celebrity obsession among adolescents is Albert Bandura's (1977) "Social Learning Theory" which suggests that people learn from one another, through observation, imitation, and modelling. It was explained that,

“Learning would be exceedingly laborious, not to mention hazardous, if people had to rely solely on the effects of their own actions to inform them what to do. Fortunately, most human behavior is learned observationally through modeling: from observing others one forms an idea of how new behaviors are performed, and on later occasions this coded information serves as a guide for action.”

The component processes of observational learning are:

- 1) Attention: it includes modelled events and observed characteristics.
- 2) Retention.
- 3) Motor Reproduction: it includes physical capabilities, self-observation, and accuracy of response,
- 4) Motivation: it includes external vicarious and self-reinforcement.

As per this theory, Celebrities work as a ‘model’ for the adolescents. Through the channel of observational learning, a celebrity can bring forward noble approaches of mindset, action and behaviours among adolescents as these young minds tend to dislike what the celebrity do not like and like what the celebrity care about. Adolescents are the most vulnerable group to the notions of the celebrities presented because adolescents find the images of celebrities very appealing which is presented via news, advertisements, movies, magazines, music, videos and various social Medias. We can understand observational learning situation in context of celebrities better through an example of television commercial of a fairness cream in which a celebrity is suggesting that using a fairness cream from a particular brand will make you popular, confident and win the admiration of others. Now depending upon the component processes absorbed (attention or motivation), the adolescents may try to imitate the behaviour of the celebrity shown in that commercial and seek to buy the product without considering any of its pros and cons.

5. Celebrity Obsession and Global Youth Culture

“Well, you know it’s interesting to see who we choose as our celebrities, and why, what makes them tick. You can learn a lot about a society by who it chooses to celebrate.”

(Woody Allen, 1998)

According to Ralf, Coffey and Williamson (1999), adolescents’ identities in the course of “youth” are usually taken as fluid and youth is also a phase of ‘transition’ during which the fundamentals of an adults’ future-self are built up.

“Global youth culture” as embraced by Kahn and Kellner (2007), is a ‘trans-disciplinary branch’ which attempts to make us understand the evolution of a complex form of hybrid culture and identity that is very commonly occurring midst the adolescents all over the globe due to the propagation of media in their everyday lives. From this standpoint adolescents could be seen to be actively responding and aware of celebrities across the whole globe presented either through music, themes and characters of films and daily soaps, printed and broadcasted news, performance in sports, business accomplishments, heart touching writings, or any other extraordinary endowments. For example, one can trace the emergence of a celebrity rapper like Eminem have started from America and now his fans are found all over the world.

Heaven and Tubridy (2007) shared that:

“Youth are seen as the part of society that is most likely to engage in a process of cultural borrowing that is disruptive of the reproduction of traditional cultural practices, from modes of dress to language, aesthetics and ideologies. From Japanese punk to Australian hip hop, youth subcultures are seen as being implicitly rebellious, born as much from a desire to reject the generation that went before them, as from identification with what they have become.”

6. Celebrity Obsession and Fan Culture

An individual who is enthusiastically devoted to someone, specially to any celebrity such as a musician or a rapper, a politician, an athlete or a sports person, a business tycoon or a scholar, an actor or an entertainer is known as his/her “fan”. Collectively, the fans of a celebrity found his/her fanbase or fandom. Usually, they try to show their devotion in a number of ways like:

- Fans are often aspired for external involvement, i.e., they try to express their connection with their favourite celebrity by going to gatherings related to their favourite celebrity, posting online about them, etc.
- Some fans like to have social interaction with other fans about their favourite celebrity, i.e., either through casual discussions, participating in fan clubs, deliberating in chat rooms, joining social media groups, attending organised get-togethers, etc.
- Some fans are willing to leave their academics and join the profession of their favourite celebrity like politics, film industry, etc.
- Some fans are ready to do anything just to get a glimpse of their favourite celebrity.
- Some fans want to meet and become friend with their favourite celebrity.
- Some fans idolise the celebrity couple. Prince Harry and Meghan Markle, Morad Osmani and Natalia Zakharova have set couple goals of numerous adolescents.
- Fans often have a ‘wish to acquire’ material objects owned or used by their favourite celebrity, such as a book signed by the original author, a bat used to play by an outstanding cricketer, a dress once worn by a favourite actress in GALA or a guitar pick used by their musical hero.
- Fans usually have interest in celebrities strong enough that they make changes in their outlook to show their devotion towards them. Getting tattoo, body piercing, haircut, hair colour and even cosmetic surgery as their favourite celebrity have.
- These adolescent fans sometimes have a crush on a celebrity.

The level of fondness and obsession among these fan-adolescents for celebrities may vary from showing interest just for entertainment purpose, to a crush, to a role model, to the mistaken belief that they know them in person and even to the level of worship. These extreme levels may develop stalking nature among adolescents which may even lead to celebrity worship syndrome. It is also probable that at these severe levels, the love for the favourite celebrity may be swapped to hatred and could result in abuse and violence because

they are not able to meet the weird expectations of their fans. This is very closely associated with the concept of a “Para-social relationship” between a fan and a celebrity, where the fans ripe a one-sided relationships with the celebrity.

7. Conclusion

The present study has presented ‘celebrity obsession’ as a universally emerging phenomenon during the adolescence period as celebrities have become an inseparable part of our daily life. In contemporary era, almost every adolescent is involved in celebrity culture either directly or indirectly because media and internet have hijacked our minds. Self-expression during this phase has become an instrument of imitation in the era of celebrity obsession the closer one looks around the world today, the more one can see that social, personal, economic and political lives are being structured around these celebrities. The adolescents try to copy them in various things like fashion trends, language, career, hobbies, make-up looks and hairstyles that these celebrities change from time to time. However, people still seem to understand very little about how this culture of celebrity obsession will look like in the future So, while studying factors influencing adolescents, Celebrity obsession should not be disregarded or ignored because the celebrities can become role models for the positive and progressive growth of adolescents and also assist them with their career and problems or the obsession can also prove to be fierce, vicious and destructive for the adolescents.

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